

CALIBRATION OF THE SOIL–PILE INTERACTION MODEL: AN APPROACH BASED ON THE NONLINEAR WINKLER MODEL

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ABSTRACT

The design of deep foundations subjected to lateral loads is a key aspect in ensuring the safety and efficiency of structures such as tall buildings, transmission towers, and offshore installations. The nonlinear Winkler model (BNWF), which represents the soil through a series of nonlinear springs using the p – y curve approach, is widely applied in geotechnical practice due to its computational efficiency and simplicity. However, the calibration of p – y curves remain a challenge, as it relies on empirical parameters and often lacks experimental validation, particularly for tropical soils found in Brazil. This study presents a numerical calibration of the soil–pile interaction model based on three-dimensional finite element simulations of lateral load tests on piles embedded in cohesive soils, performed using the ABAQUS® software. The calibration was carried out by varying key soil parameters, including cohesion (c), elastic modulus (E_s), and Poisson's ratio (ν_s), along with the soil–pile interface friction coefficient (μ). The results were compared with the semi-empirical p – y curves recommended by the American Petroleum Institute (API) for soft clays. As a practical contribution, the study provides representative parameter ranges for cohesive soils, suitable for application in design software based on the Winkler model. These findings aim to improve the accuracy of p – y curve applications in engineering practice and support more reliable structural analysis of pile foundations under lateral loads.

KEYWORDS: Soil-pile interaction, nonlinear Winkler model, p - y curves, ABAQUS, foundations.

I. INTRODUCTION

The design of deep foundations requires a careful assessment of the interaction between the soil and structural elements, particularly in situations where lateral loads predominate, such as in tall and slender buildings, structures subjected to wind or seismic actions, transmission towers, and offshore platforms. In these cases, the performance of piles must be evaluated not only in terms of their load-bearing capacity, but also with respect to lateral displacements and the overall stiffness of the foundation system.

The response of piles under lateral loading is recognized as one of the most complex soil–structure interaction problems in geotechnical engineering. The primary function of a single pile or a pile group is to transfer superstructure loads to the surrounding soil without causing excessive displacements at the pile head. The analysis of this problem is not straightforward, as it depends directly on the stress–strain response of the soil mass, which exhibits strong nonlinear behaviour. Three-dimensional finite element (FEM) or finite difference methods (FDM) can be applied to address this issue. However, in practice, these approaches present limitations, either due to the extensive effort required for data preparation or the high computational cost. For this reason, simplified approaches such as the Winkler model (p – y curves) remain widely adopted in engineering practice, as they are easier to implement and can be validated by more advanced numerical simulations ([1], [2]).

Among the available alternatives to represent the lateral response of piles, the generalized Winkler model is one of the most applied. In this approach, the relationship between the soil reaction (p) and the lateral displacement (y) along the pile shaft is represented by functions known as p – y curves. These

curves can be derived using different approaches, with semi-empirical formulations being frequently employed, combining back-analysis of lateral load tests with stress–strain curves obtained from laboratory triaxial tests ([3], [4], [5], [6], [7]).

Recent advances have highlighted the limitations of traditional p – y curve formulations when applied to cohesive soils, especially soft clays, where empirical models may overestimate stiffness or ultimate resistance. Large-scale tests and numerical simulations have sought to refine these models by incorporating soil-specific properties and cyclic loading effects [8], [9]. More recently, alternative procedures have been proposed to numerically derive p – y curves for cohesive soils, aiming to improve design reliability and reduce dependence on purely empirical correlations [10]. These developments reinforce the need for updated calibration strategies when applying the Winkler model to tropical clays, such as those found in Brazil.

The objective of this study is to numerically simulate the lateral load test of a pile embedded in cohesive soil to obtain representative p – y curves for soil–pile interaction. To achieve this, a numerical model was developed and calibrated using the finite element software ABAQUS®, with reference to the semi-empirical methods recommended by [3] for soft clays. The calibration process was carried out by varying the following soil parameters: cohesion (c), elastic modulus (E_s), and Poisson's ratio (ν_s). In addition, the influence of the soil–pile interface friction coefficient (μ) was also investigated. As a contribution to foundation design, this study proposes representative parameter ranges for application in design software, aiming to improve the accuracy and reliability of structural analyses.

This paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the numerical model developed in ABAQUS® to simulate soil–pile interaction. Section III details the calibration process and the parametric analyses. Section IV discusses the results and their comparison with theoretical models from the literature. Finally, Section V summarizes the main conclusions and suggests directions for future research.

II. NUMERICAL MODEL OF SOIL–PILE INTERACTION

The numerical modelling was developed using the finite element software ABAQUS®, version 2019. The model consists of a solid circular pile embedded in the surrounding soil, including the interface between the pile and the soil. Due to symmetry with respect to the longitudinal plane, only half of the model was simulated. Appropriate boundary conditions were applied to the symmetry plane. The geometry of the model is illustrated in Figure 1. Fixed boundary conditions in the x , y , and z directions were applied to the lateral and bottom surfaces. The model dimensions were based on [14], where the dimensions in the x , y , and z directions were set to $20D$, $10D$, and $(L + 3)$, respectively, with D and L representing the pile diameter and length.

The material properties used in the simulation are presented in Table 1. The soil parameters adopted in this study were obtained from empirical correlations provided by [15], based on the Standard Penetration Test (SPT). This method of estimating soil strength is widely used in Brazil and was therefore employed in the present work.

The numerical analyses were carried out by applying displacement-controlled loading to the structure, which provides better precision and control when the system reaches its ultimate resistance. This approach also improves the convergence behaviour of the numerical model. The horizontal loading applied to the pile followed geotechnical engineering practice as described by [14], where a displacement equivalent to 3% of the pile diameter was imposed at the pile head, a value near the ultimate failure of the system.

The generation of the p – y curves in ABAQUS® was performed after processing the model, using the principal stress component (S_{11}) and the corresponding displacement (U_1), both in the x -direction. To evaluate the points with the highest stress concentration, the p – y curves were generated for a depth (z) of 0.5 m. The soil reactions (p , in force per unit length) at the specified depth were calculated by multiplying the stress S_{11} at the evaluation point by the pile diameter (D). This procedure enabled the generation of the p – y curve, relating the soil reaction (p) to the horizontal displacement (y) at the analysed point.

Figure 1. Three-dimensional numerical model of soil–pile interaction.

Table 1. Material parameters used in the numerical simulation [15].

Material	Parameter	Value
Concrete	Unit weight, γ (kN/m ³)	24
	Poisson's ratio, ν	0.15
	Elastic modulus, E_{cs} (MPa)	24150
Soil: Soft Clay	SPT blow count, N_{spt}	5
	Effective unit weight, γ' (kN/m ³)	15
	Poisson's ratio, ν_s	0.23
	Elastic modulus, E_s (MPa)	5.25
	Coefficient of lateral earth pressure, K_0	1.0
	Cohesion, c (kPa)	50
	Internal friction angle, ϕ (°)	0
Dilatancy angle, ψ (°)	0	

III. NUMERICAL MODEL CALIBRATION

The calibration of the three-dimensional simulations performed in ABAQUS® was conducted using the semi-empirical method proposed in [3] for soft clays, specifically the model developed by Matlock (1970). The soil was modelled as an elastoplastic material following the Mohr–Coulomb failure criterion. The calibration process involved varying the following soil parameters: cohesion (c), elastic modulus (E_s), and Poisson's ratio (ν_s). The friction coefficient (μ) at the soil–pile interface was also evaluated.

3.1. Modelling Methodology in ABAQUS®

A total of 38 simulation cases were performed, organized into four main groups, followed by two additional stages involving parameter adjustments to optimize the results. The parameters calibrated include Poisson's ratio (ν_s), elastic modulus (E_s), cohesion (c), and the soil–pile friction coefficient (μ). Table 2 summarizes the parametric analysis groups used for model calibration.

In Group 1, the Poisson's ratio (ν_s) was varied, with values ranging from 0.10 (typical of highly compressible soils) to 0.495 (near the theoretical incompressibility limit). Group 2 examined the influence of the elastic modulus (E_s), testing values from 4500 kPa (very soft clays) to 15000 kPa (more

rigid materials). This range allowed assessment of how changes in initial stiffness affect the soil response.

In Group 3, the cohesion (c) was varied from 10 kPa (very soft clays) to 50 kPa (higher undrained shear strength). Group 4 investigated the soil–pile interface friction coefficient (μ), ranging from 0.20 (smooth interfaces) to 1.00 (extremely rough conditions).

Table 2. Summary of the parametric analysis conducted for numerical model calibration.

Group	Varied Parameter	Tested Values	Cases	Fixed Parameters
1	Poisson's Ratio (ν_s)	0.100; 0.300; 0.400; 0.495	1–4	$E_s = 5250$ kPa; $c = 50$ kPa; $\mu = 0.48$
2	Elastic Modulus (E_s)	4500 kPa; 8000 kPa; 11500 kPa; 15000 kPa	5–8	$\nu_s = 0.23$; $c = 50$ kPa; $\mu = 0.48$
3	Cohesion (c)	10 kPa; 20 kPa; 30 kPa; 40 kPa	9–12	$\nu_s = 0.23$; $E_s = 5250$ kPa; $\mu = 0.48$
4	Friction Coefficient (μ)	0.20; 0.60; 0.80; 1.00	13–16	$\nu_s = 0.23$; $E_s = 5250$ kPa; $c = 50$ kPa
–	Parameter Combinations	–	17–36	Multiple combinations
–	Optimized Cases	–	37–38	$\nu_s = 0.23$ – 0.30 ; $E_s = 11500$ kPa; $c = 30$ kPa; $\mu = 0.48$

Complementing this parametric study, additional simulations were performed using combinations of the calibrated parameters to assess the fit to the p – y curve. Finally, optimized cases (Cases 37 and 38) were defined to refine the modelling. In Case 37, the following parameters were adopted: $\nu_s = 0.23$ (reference value), $E_s = 11500$ kPa, $\mu = 0.48$ (value commonly used in geotechnical practice), and $c = 30$ kPa (intermediate value among those tested). In Case 38, a refinement was made by using $\nu_s = 0.30$ (more representative of soft clay compressibility), while maintaining $E_s = 11500$ kPa, $c = 30$ kPa, and $\mu = 0.48$.

3.2. Analysis of Soil Parameter Influence on the p – y Curve

The parametric analysis involved 38 cases, in which each parameter was individually varied or combined, enabling identification of:

- How each parameter influences the initial stiffness, ultimate resistance, and plateau behaviour of the p – y curve;
- Which combinations yield the closest approximation to the behaviour predicted by the theoretical model; and
- Physical and numerical limitations associated with extreme parameter values.

3.2.1. Parametric Analysis of the Variation in Poisson's Ratio (ν_s)

The present analysis investigates the variation of Poisson's ratio (ν_s) within the range of 0.10 to 0.495. A comparison is conducted between the numerical model and the theoretical model, considering soft clay with an elastic modulus of 5250 kPa, cohesion of 50 kPa, and a friction coefficient of 0.48. The results are presented in Figure 2, where solid lines and dashed lines represent the results of the numerical and theoretical models, respectively.

It is important to emphasize that low values of Poisson's ratio ($\nu_s = 0.10$) represent soils with low compressibility, characterized by smaller volumetric strains under loading. Conversely, high values ($\nu_s = 0.495$) indicate high compressibility, due to greater energy dissipation in lateral deformations. The

Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion, adopted in the numerical model, considers only cohesion (c) as the strength parameter, assuming $\phi = 0^\circ$ under undrained conditions. This differs from the Matlock model [4], which captures experimentally observed nonlinearities.

Figure 2. Parametric analysis of the variation in Poisson's ratio.

Upon examining the results presented in Figure 2, it is observed that in the plastic region of the curves, lower v_s values (0.10 to 0.30) result in a more deformable numerical p - y curve. This can be interpreted as the soil exhibiting greater resistance to lateral deformation (lower v_s), leading to a reduced “detachment” or “gap” between the soil and the pile. As a result, lateral stresses are redistributed more effectively around the pile. Consequently, since the soil does not easily deform, the lateral load applied at the pile head is dissipated less efficiently into the surrounding medium, resulting in greater lateral displacements (y) for the same load level (p).

In contrast, as shown in Figure 2, higher values of v_s (0.40 and 0.495) produce a less deformable numerical curve. For this result, it is understood that due to the magnitude of v_s , the soil deforms more easily in the lateral direction, leading to greater “separation” around the pile. This behaviour allows for increased mobilization of resistance, as the soil redistributes itself to balance geostatic stresses. Thus, the applied lateral load is more effectively dissipated into the surrounding medium, reducing lateral displacement (y).

Another aspect observed from Figure 2 is the behaviour of the elastic region, where a significant divergence is noted between the theoretical and numerical models. This indicates the need for further calibration of the remaining parameters to improve the agreement between the curves.

3.2.2. Parametric Analysis of the Variation in Elastic Modulus (E_s)

Figure 3 presents a comparison between the numerical results (solid line) and the theoretical Matlock model [4] (dashed line) for different values of the soil elastic modulus E_s (ranging from 4500 kPa to 15000 kPa), while keeping the other parameters constant ($v_s = 0.23$; $c = 50$ kPa; $\mu = 0.48$).

Upon analysing the results shown in Figure 3, it is observed that the initial stiffness of the p - y curve is sensitive to variations in the elastic modulus (E_s). For Case 5 (4500 kPa), the curve becomes significantly more flexible and less stiff. As E_s increases, in Cases 6 (8000 kPa) and 7 (11500 kPa), the initial stiffness tends to approach that of the theoretical curve, with Case 7 showing the best agreement

in the displacement range $y < 4$ mm. The highest value of E_s , in Case 8 (15000 kPa), did not adequately represent the curve behaviour in this simulation.

Figure 3. Parametric analysis of the variation in the soil elastic modulus.

A verification was performed by calculating the initial stiffness (k) for displacements $y < 2$ mm using the generalized Hooke's law ($k = p/y$). It was found that extreme E_s values (4500 kPa or 15000 kPa) lead to a theoretical model with an initial stiffness much higher than the numerical one ($\Delta k > 74\%$). In contrast, intermediate models with E_s values of 8000 kPa or 11500 kPa cause the theoretical model to present an initial stiffness approximately 60% greater than the numerical model.

Following this comparative analysis, it is suggested that for an adequate calibration of the numerical model, the elastic modulus should be selected based not only on the initial stiffness but also on the post-elastic response. It is emphasized that the choice of E_s should consider a realistic range, as excessively high values may overestimate the soil stiffness, while very low values may underestimate it. Therefore, intermediate values ranging from 8000 kPa to 11500 kPa will be considered for the subsequent simulations, as they showed the best balance between the elastic phase representation and the transition to the plastic regime.

3.2.3. Parametric Analysis of Cohesion Variation (c)

In this analysis, the soil cohesion was varied (10 to 50 kPa), and a comparison was made between the numerical model (ABAQUS®) and the theoretical model proposed by [4]. The results are presented in Figure 4 (dashed line: theoretical model; solid line: numerical model).

Upon examining the curves in Figure 4, it is observed that for soils with very low cohesion (10 kPa), the interparticle bonding is weaker, resulting in increased deformability. The plastic behaviour of the curve also reveals lower resistance and a faster collapse of the soil. In such cases, Andersen (2015) recommends that the curves be calibrated using experimental data, as theoretical models may overestimate the initial stiffness of the soil.

For clays with cohesion values of 20 kPa and 50 kPa (Figure 4), the numerical model shows good agreement with the theoretical curve in the plastic region. However, when cohesion values of 30 kPa and 40 kPa are used, the curves significantly exceed the maximum resistance predicted by the theoretical model. Therefore, it is important to combine intermediate cohesion values with other parameters to better approximate the response curves.

Figure 4. Parametric analysis of cohesion variation.

3.2.4. Parametric Analysis of the Variation of the Soil–Pile Friction Coefficient (μ)

The variation of the friction coefficient (μ) at the soil–pile interface has significant impacts on load transfer and on the behaviour of the p–y curve, as evidenced by the numerical (solid line) and theoretical (dashed line) results presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Parametric analysis of the variation of the soil–pile friction coefficient.

The analysis of the results in Figure 4 shows that the numerical model underestimates the initial stiffness when compared to Matlock model [4]. In the plastic phase, it is observed that the extreme values (0.20 and 1.00) increase the divergence between the numerical and theoretical curves, while the intermediate

values (0.48, 0.60, and 0.80) bring the curves closer. When $\mu = 0.20$, the lateral resistance is governed by cohesion rather than by friction at the interface. Conversely, when friction is very high ($\mu = 1.00$), full adhesion between the soil and the pile is assumed, with no slippage, which may be regarded as a rare condition in soft clays due to creep and particle rearrangement.

Experimental and numerical studies commonly adopt $\mu = 0.48$ as the optimal value for soil–pile interaction modelling in soft clays. [13] demonstrated in comparative foundation analyses that this value provides the best correlation between numerical and theoretical models, balancing resistance mobilization and realistic system behaviour.

3.2.5. Parametric Analysis of the Variation in the Combination of Geotechnical Parameters

In the analysis of parameter combinations, 16 simulations were performed. For Cases 17–20 (Figure 6a), cohesion was varied (sequentially: 10 kPa, 50 kPa, 20 kPa, and 30 kPa), while maintaining constant values for the intermediate elastic modulus ($E_s = 11500$ kPa), low Poisson’s ratio ($\nu_s = 0.1$), and high friction coefficient ($\mu = 1.0$). In Cases 21–24 (Figure 6b), the same configuration as Cases 17–20 was adopted, but $\mu = 0.48$ was considered. In Cases 25–28 (Figure 6c), the configuration of Cases 21–24 was maintained, modifying only the elastic modulus to $E_s = 8000$ kPa. Finally, in Cases 29–32 (Figure 6d), Poisson’s ratio was varied (sequentially: 0.23, 0.30, 0.40, and 0.495), while considering intermediate values of elastic modulus ($E_s = 11500$ kPa) and friction coefficient ($\mu = 0.48$), and high cohesion ($c = 50$ kPa).

Figure 6. Parametric analysis of the combination of geotechnical parameters.

From the analysis of the data presented in Figure 6a, it is observed that increasing cohesion ($c = 10$ kPa to 50 kPa) results in a gradual increase in soil resistance, reducing horizontal displacements under the same applied load. This behaviour is consistent with Mohr–Coulomb theory, which highlights cohesion as a key factor in the stress–strain response of cohesive soils. The numerical curves exhibit a nonlinear relationship, typical of elastoplastic materials, where soils with low cohesion display greater deformability and a tendency toward brittle failure, while more cohesive soils show higher stiffness and a more gradual transition to the plastic regime (ductile behaviour).

The results in Figure 6b, with a reduced friction coefficient ($\mu = 0.48$), show a smoother transition between the elastic and plastic phases of the curves. This difference occurs because the lower friction coefficient decreases shear resistance, making the soil–pile system more deformable and less prone to abrupt failures. The numerical curves maintain the nonlinear relationship between soil pressure and lateral displacement, but with less steep slopes, indicating greater ductility.

According to the results illustrated in Figure 6c, the soil exhibits more deformable behaviour compared with the previous cases. The lower elastic modulus indicates higher compressibility of the material, which is reflected in more pronounced horizontal displacements for the same level of applied load. The numerical curves present steeper inclinations in the elastic phase, evidencing a more flexible soil response.

Finally, Figure 6d shows that higher values of ν_s (close to 0.5) make the p – y curve stiffer. This trend had already been observed in the analysis of Figure 2; however, the curve presented in Figure 6d shows more pronounced stiffness because of the increase in the elastic modulus (from 5250 kPa to 11500 kPa). It is also observed that the increase in cohesion to 50 kPa, combined with the higher E_s , resulted in numerical curves with greater resistance than the theoretical curve.

3.2.6. Parametric Analysis of the Optimized Cases

This analysis was carried out by selectively adjusting the parameters. To better understand the modified data, Table 3 presents the parameters considered in the analysis of Cases 33–38.

Table 3. Modified soil parameters for the optimized cases.

Soft Clay Parameters	Cases					
	33	34	35	36	37	38
Standard Penetration Test index, N_{spt}	5	5	5	5	5	5
Unit weight, γ (kN/m ³)	15	15	15	15	15	15
Poisson's ratio, ν_s	0.23	0.23	0.495	0.1	0.23	0.3
Elastic modulus, E_s (kPa)	8000	11500	11500	11500	11500	11500
Cohesion, c (kPa)	30	30	30	30	30	30
Lateral earth pressure coefficient, K_0	1	1	1	1	1	1
Internal friction angle, ϕ (°)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Dilation angle, ψ (°)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Friction coefficient, μ	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.48	0.48
Stiffness ratio (E/c)	267	383	383	383	383	383

The numerical results (solid line), compared with the theoretical curve (dashed line), are presented in Figures 7a and 7b.

From Figure 7a, it can be observed that Cases 33 to 36, with $\mu = 0.80$, exhibit stiffer curves and greater divergence from the theoretical response, especially in Case 35 ($\nu_s = 0.495$), where the high Poisson's ratio (ν_s) amplified lateral displacements. This phenomenon is consistent with the theory of [14], which associates high ν_s values with increased volumetric compressibility under loading.

Cases 37 and 38 (highlighted in Figure 7b), in which the friction coefficient was reduced to $\mu = 0.48$, show significant convergence with the theoretical curve, indicating greater agreement between the

models. This reduction in soil–pile friction results in a smoother transition between the elastic and plastic phases, reflecting lower shear stiffness at the interface and higher soil ductility. Moreover, the maintenance of $E_s = 11500$ kPa and $c = 30$ kPa in these cases reinforces that the friction coefficient in soil–pile interaction is a key parameter governing the deformability of the system.

Figure 7. Parametric analysis of the optimized cases.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study addressed the calibration of a numerical model for soil–pile interaction using three-dimensional finite element analyses in ABAQUS®, with reference to the semi-empirical method proposed by [4] for soft clays. A parametric study was conducted to investigate the influence of Poisson’s ratio (ν_s), elastic modulus (E_s), cohesion (c), and soil–pile interface friction coefficient (μ) on the p–y curves.

The main findings can be summarized as follows:

- Poisson’s ratio (ν_s): intermediate values (0.23–0.30) showed greater agreement with the theoretical model, since they balanced the effect of transverse and longitudinal soil deformations on the p–y curve behaviour;
- Elastic modulus (E_s): intermediate values (8000 kPa and 11,500 kPa) better captured the initial stiffness, the transition to the plastic regime, and the ultimate stiffness;
- Cohesion (c): the range of 20–30 kPa provided results closer to the theoretical model, while extreme values (10 kPa or 50 kPa) led to over/underestimation of resistance;
- Soil–pile friction coefficient (μ): the value $\mu = 0.48$ proved to be the most appropriate, corroborating previous studies ([13]).

In summary, the optimized cases (37 and 38) provided the best fit to the theoretical model curve, especially in the plastic behavior phase. However, discrepancies still exist in the initial stiffness of the curve. For the numerical model to more closely follow the theoretical curve, a significant increase in E_s and c would be required, which would result in higher resistance in the numerical p–y curve.

The results of this study confirm that the calibration of soil–pile interaction models in cohesive soils remains a critical task in geotechnical engineering. The discrepancies observed between numerical and empirical curves are consistent with recent findings from large-scale and cyclic loading studies on clayey soils [8], [9]. Furthermore, the adoption of numerical derivation techniques for p–y curves, as

proposed in recent offshore and onshore investigations [10], provides a promising path to enhance model reliability. In this context, the parameter ranges calibrated in this research may serve as a practical reference for cohesive soils, complementing and extending the approaches reported in the literature.

Based on this, the following limitations and future recommendations are noted:

- (i) the model adopted in this study assumes soil homogeneity, while real conditions may present heterogeneities. Thus, it is suggested that models for stratified soils be simulated;
- (ii) the Mohr–Coulomb criterion, although widely applied, simplifies the stress–strain response of soft clays. Therefore, it is recommended to explore and test alternative failure criteria and incorporate them into the numerical model;
- (iii) another important consideration is that theoretical curves may overestimate the resistance of soft clays, making calibration through experimental tests necessary.

As a practical contribution to foundation design, it is highlighted that:

- (1) the parameter range obtained from the calibration can be used as a starting point in software that employs the Winkler model, such as LPILE or custom spreadsheet implementations;
- (2) when experimental data are available, it is recommended to adjust the values of elastic modulus (E_s) and cohesion (c) using empirical correlations with field data; and
- (3) it is recommended that parameters always comply with the criteria established in [15].

Therefore, this study intends to contribute as a parameterized reference for geotechnical design of soil–pile interaction in cohesive soils.

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